

Stability Constants of some Bivalent Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone Oxime

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THE present communication reports the determination of stability constants of Pd^{II}, Cu^{II}, VO^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone oxime (HDMAOX) at 27 ± 0.2° in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at different ionic strengths.

Experimental

The ligand (HDMAOX) was prepared as reported earlier¹.

The following sets of solutions were titrated against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution (0.05 M): (i) 0.05 M HClO₄, (ii) (i) + 0.01 M HDMAOX and (iii) (ii) + 0.008 M metal ion.

The apparent volume of 75% dioxane + 25% water mixture (v/v) was multiplied by appropriate correction factor² to obtain the real volume. Ionic strengths of 0.1, 0.05 and 0.01 M were maintained by adding required amount of NaClO₄. The pH measurements were made on a Systronic 335 digital pH-meter and corrected by using Van Uitert and Hass equation³. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants (Table 1) were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁴.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH HDMAOX AT 27 ± 0.2° IN 75% DIOXANE MEDIUM AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Cation	$\mu = 0.1 M$		$\mu = 0.05 M$		$\mu = 0.01 M$	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
(H ⁺)	10.80	—	10.90	—	11.15	—
Pd ^{II}	11.45	10.20	11.51	10.95	11.72	10.61
Cu ^{II}	11.00	9.75	11.15	9.85	11.40	10.00
VO ^{II}	10.50	9.67	10.63	9.71	10.83	9.81
UO ₂ ^{II}	10.05	9.40	10.20	9.47	10.48	9.59
Be ^{II}	8.70	7.72	8.88	7.80	9.15	7.91
Zn ^{II}	8.30	6.75	8.46	6.87	8.70	7.05
Ni ^{II}	8.02	5.95	8.25	5.50	8.65	5.71
Co ^{II}	7.25	5.80	7.38	5.91	7.58	6.09
Mn ^{II}	6.17	5.70	6.37	5.81	6.72	6.00
Cd ^{II}	5.20	4.17	5.38	4.23	5.72	4.35

Results and Discussions

The ligand (HDMAOX) behaved as a monoprotic acid due to deprotonation of the phenolic OH group *ortho* to the oximino group from which the proton was replaced by the metal ions during complex formation. This was evident from the fact that the metal titration curves were well-separated from the ligand titration curves.

Values of $\bar{n} > 2$ were not obtained in any case which suggested that there are only two complexes, viz 1:1 and 1:2 in the systems. The order of stability constants of bivalent metal complexes was found to be: Pd^{II} > Cu^{II} > VO^{II} > UO₂^{II} > Be^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II} > Cd^{II}, which is in agreement with the Irving-Williams⁵ order.

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Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of some Trivalent Rare Earths with *p,p'*-Bromosulphonosalicylidene Anil

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IN this communication we report the result of our potentiometric investigation of the Schiff base ligand (H₂L) *p,p'*-bromosulphonosalicylidene anil and its complexes with trivalent rare earth metal ions like Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}. The study has been carried out in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° using Calvin-Bjerrum¹ pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti². The ionic strength (*I*) has been maintained approximately constant at 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand: The Schiff base ligand *p,p'*-bromosulphonosalicylidene anil was prepared as described earlier³ and purity of the compound was checked by elemental analysis.

Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution and double distilled water were used. Rare earth metals were estimated by EDTA method⁴. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M HClO₄ to avoid metal hydrolysis.

pH titration: Following sets of titrations were performed at 25 (Fig. 1), 35 and 45° against standard alkali solution (~0.4 M): (i) 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 35 ml water, (ii) 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 20 ml 4 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 15 ml water and (iii) 5 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 5 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution + 20 ml 4 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 15 ml water.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curve at 25° ($I=0.1 M NaClO_4$): (□) acid, (Δ) ligand, (○) Sm, (●) Pr, (■) Nd and (▲) Gd.

The total volume in each case was kept constant (50 ml) initially and the ratio of the metal salt to reagent was maintained 1:4 in all titrations in order to satisfy the maximum coordination possibility of the metal ions. A ECIL 5651 digital pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) with combined glass electrode assembly was used for the measurement

of pH. Before each set of readings the pH-meter was calibrated with standard buffers and after completion of the whole set, the calibration was again checked to confirm the reproducibility of the data.

Results and Discussion

The $\bar{n}_H$ values extended over a range of 0.25–2.54. Proton-ligand stability constants, $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_3^H$ values are summarised in Table 1. Here $\log K_1^H$ refers to the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen attached to the salicylaldehyde moiety⁵ and $\log K_2^H$ to the deprotonation of the sulphonic acid group. Hydrogen attached to the less basic azomethine nitrogen will be the first to dissociate and hence $\log K_1^H$ value has been assigned to the proton dissociation of NH^+ . The K_1^H value of similar magnitude has also been observed⁶ in a known compound containing SO_3H group.

The $\bar{n}$ values for metal ions lie over the range $0 < \bar{n} < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n} < 2$ indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The metal curve showed departure from the ligand curve at pH values much lower than the pH of metal hydrolysis⁷. The possibility of formation of polynuclear complexes was ignored due to very low concentration of the metal ion used. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values (metal-ligand stability constant) were evaluated using usual computational method^{8,9} (Table 1). The $\log K$ values when plotted against $e^{\Delta H}/r$ show an increasing trend with a break at gadolinium. Certain amount of ionic character may therefore be suggested for metal-ligand bonding although the possibility of some covalent interaction cannot be completely excluded⁹.

The enthalpy term ΔH is favourable for complexation as reflected by the negative values in all the cases. The negative entropy (ΔS) values are not favourable for complexation. Such

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 25°

Cation	Temp. °C	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K_3	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H ⁺	25	8.45	6.00	3.40			
	35	7.95	5.80	3.35			
	45	7.65	5.65	3.30			
Pr ^{III}	25	5.25	3.85	—			
	35	5.20	3.75	—	12.4	13.7	4
	45	5.15	3.65	—			
Nd ^{III}	25	4.75	3.95	—			
	35	4.70	3.68	—	11.9	20.5	29
	45	4.65	3.20	—			
Sm ^{III}	25	6.95	4.55	—			
	35	6.25	4.10	—	15.7	41.1	85
	45	5.49	4.05	—			
Gd ^{III}	25	4.80	4.05	—			
	35	4.75	3.65	—	12.1	19.7	5
	45	4.64	3.55	—			

unfavourable negative contribution of entropy may arise due to the restriction of degrees of freedom of solvent molecules in the vicinity of the metal ion and this effect is very much pronounced with metal ions of high charge¹⁰ and nature of the ligand. The log *K* values reported here are accurate to ± 0.3 log units and the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are reliable to ± 0.04 kcal mol⁻¹, ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ and 2 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

The order of stability of trivalent metal complexes follows the sequence, Pr^{III} > Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}. Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon in the case of lanthanides¹¹ and this may be traced to be due to varying degree of stabilisations arising out of interaction of 4*f* metal orbitals with ligand field¹².

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Polarographic Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with some Amino Acids as Primary Ligands and 2,2'-Bipyridyl as Secondary Ligand

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INERACTION of cadmium(II) with amino acids and 2,2'-bipyridyl (BP) has been investigated polarographically by many workers¹. The ternary systems of Cd^{II} with BP as primary ligand and

amino acids as secondary ligands have also been studied by pH-titration method². As no polarographic studies on ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine (GL), DL- α -alanine (AL) and DL-valine (VL) as primary ligands and BP as secondary ligand have so far been made, we report the results herein.

Experimental

Stock solutions of the ligands glycine (B.D.H.), DL- α -alanine (B.D.H.), DL-valine (SD's) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (AnalaR) were prepared in double-distilled water. Stock solution of CdCl₂·6H₂O (SISCO) was prepared in nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis and its metal content was determined by titration with EDTA³. 'Mercury for polarography' (E. Merck) was used for the DME.

Polarographic measurements were performed with 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ Cd^{II} and 0.001% Triton X-100 at *I* = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃) and at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions to remove dissolved oxygen.

Polarograms were recorded on a Toshniwal CLO2B digital polarograph. The DME had *t* = 4 s (open-circuit) at *h*₀₁₁ = 49 cm (35.25 cm in case of Cd^{II}-BP system). All potentials refer to SCE. pH measurements were made on a ELICO LI-120 digital pH-meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes.

The protonation constants of amino acids were determined by Irving and Rossotti method⁴.

Results and Discussion

Dissociation constants (Table 1) of ligands were calculated from the pH-titration data using Rossotti and Rossotti's method⁵. For BP, the values given are taken from literature⁶.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS
I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), Temp. = 35°

Ligand	p <i>K</i> ₁	p <i>K</i> ₂
Glycine ^a	9.55	
DL- α -Alanine ^a	9.70	
DL-Valine ^a	9.51	
2,2'-Bipyridyl ^b	4.40	2.80

^aPresent work. ^bRef. 6.

Binary systems: The studies of binary and ternary systems were made under identical conditions⁷.

The reduction of Cd^{II} gave a single, reversible and diffusion-controlled wave in absence and presence of ligands. An increase in ligand concentration or pH shifted the half-wave potential of Cd^{II} to more negative values indicating the complex formation between the metal ion and the ligand.

In case of amino acids as ligand, pH was adjusted with KOH. The total concentration of amino

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